

DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY BASED ON CLUSTER APPROACH

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Introduction

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the rapid development of one of the important branches of industry - the textile industry. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 of October 23, 2019, processing of agricultural associations, farmers and peasant farms in the "Strategy of the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" the tasks of ensuring mutual cooperation with industrial enterprises (including clusters) are defined.

Based on this, as one of the important factors of the development of the country's economy, it is considered one of the urgent issues to develop recommendations on the basis of a detailed study of the possibilities of development of the textile industry based on the cluster approach.

Analyses and results

The importance of the textile industry in the economic development of our republic is increasing. Today, the textile industry accounts for 14.9 percent of the industrial gross product (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of textile industry development in the republic

Processed fruit and vegetable products	Unit	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022 with the basis of 2018, In %
Production index of textile, clothing, leather products compared to the previous year, in percentage	%	105,4	104,9	113,8	118,8	108,8	+3,4
The share of production of textiles,	%	14,5	12,6	13,2	14,9	14,9	+0,4

clothing, and leather products in the industrial output							
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Source: based on the information of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

From the given data, it is known that in 2018-2022, the average annual growth rate of textile industry production was 10.3% compared to previous years. The share of production of textiles, clothing, and leather products in the total manufacturing industry increased from 14.5 to 14.9%.

At the same time, according to the researches, stable, strong and long-term integration relations of processing enterprises with raw material suppliers and sellers in domestic and foreign markets are not sufficiently established in the textile industry today.

In the decision PQ-4186 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 12, 2019 "On measures to further deepen the reform of the textile and sewing and knitting industry and expand its export potential", starting from the cultivation of raw cotton, the initial processing, the implementation of a cluster model of development, which provides for the integration of production up to the stage of further processing and production of finished textile products with high added value in cotton ginning enterprises, is defined.

According to the information, "the term "cluster" was introduced into the scientific process in the 80s of the 20th century by M. Porter as an economic category. According to him, a cluster is a geographically inter-branch union of companies and institutions operating in a certain field" [5].

"Cluster" in the textile industry is a group of farmers and peasant farms, processing industry enterprises operating in a technological system of production, processing, storage and sale of raw cotton, working in a unified manner towards the single goal of storage, logistics and sale infrastructures. means a unified structure.

It should be noted that in such specialization, producers are connected to each other, but this does not mean that they are dependent on each other. On the contrary, complete independence is ensured in the choice of production lines and partners. Each enterprise deals with a stage of the production process that cannot function without each other. Distribution of the production process

among a large number of firms ensures a high degree of specialization in complementary production stages.

The competitive advantage of clustered enterprises is important in three aspects:

- deep specialization;
- cooperative and mutually beneficial cooperation;
- effective product quality control.

The implementation of clusters in the cotton industry was initially based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 "On Measures for the Rapid Development of the Textile and Sewing-Knitting Industry" No. PF-5285 and its implementation No. 53 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 25, 2018 "On measures to introduce modern forms of organization of cotton-textile production" and dated March 31, 2018 "Cotton-to It started with the decisions No. 253 "On additional measures for the organization of activities of textile productions and clusters". According to these decisions:

- 16 cotton ginning enterprises and 68 cotton processing points located in the area of cotton-textile production and clusters have been inspected, and their buildings and equipment will be paid to the cotton-textile clusters for a period of 5 years. , sale with the condition of modernization of production for no more than 2 years;

- effective and rational use of land, water and other resources by cotton-textile clusters, increasing productivity and assisting farmers in timely harvesting of cotton raw materials;

- allocating loans at a preferential rate of 3% from the funds of the State Support Fund for Agriculture under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the financing of cotton cultivation;

- for farms on the purchase of agricultural machinery on the basis of leasing, the supply of mineral fertilizers, seeds, fuels and lubricants, chemical plant protection agents and other material resources apply the stipulated conditions and procedures to cotton-textile clusters;

- a number of measures were established, such as independent sales of cultivated and processed products to consumers through direct contracts and stock exchanges.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 No. PF-5285 "On measures for rapid development of the textile and sewing and knitting industry":

- From the harvest of 2020, the practice of determining the purchase price of raw cotton will be abandoned, and producers of raw cotton (farms, cotton-textile clusters, cooperatives) will be given the right to freely place regionalized cotton varieties;

- State support of Agriculture by commercial banks to finance the costs of cotton production by farms, cotton-textile clusters, cooperatives and elite seed farms within the seed development center 8% of the total cost of cotton raw materials grown for a period of 12 months from the funds of the fund, up to 50% of the total value of cotton, and up to 60% of the total cost of cotton, up to 10% of the annual loan (including 2% bank margin).

According to the data, the clusters provide economic efficiency by introducing innovative ideas and cost-effective technologies in agriculture. For example, last year "TST cluster" in Kuychichirchik district and "Sangzor textile" cluster in Dostlik district produced an average of 30-35 quintals of threshing cotton per hectare, increasing productivity by almost 2 times compared to the previous year. "Khanteks" cluster in Korgontepa district obtained an average yield of up to 70 centners in cotton fields where drip irrigation was introduced [4].

According to the analysis, today there are the following problems in the development of cotton-textile clusters:

- in some regions, farmers are forced to join the cluster, not on a voluntary basis, that is, they do not have the opportunity to choose the cluster;
- the transfer of money for raw cotton grown by clusters to farmers is taking longer;
- clusters somewhat limit the economic freedom of farmers.

The establishment of one specialized cluster within one region will undoubtedly lead to the cluster occupying a monopoly position and suffocating the competitive environment. If we take into account that restriction of monopoly and development of competitive environment are defined as one of the most important directions of economic reforms in our republic today, clustering processes should not lead to increase of monopolistic structures in local areas.

Conclusions and recommendations

In our opinion, it is appropriate to implement the following measures for the rapid and stable development of the textile industry:

- the farm independently solves the issue of cluster membership and which cluster to choose;
- to make advance payments (for 60% of the value of the harvest) and make the final settlement at the end of the year (for the remaining 40%) by concluding "futures contracts" in advance;
- absolutely not allow one cluster to have a monopoly position in one area;
- reducing production costs in exchange for increasing the level of utilization of production facilities and labor productivity;
- application of innovation in the areas of effective diversification of production and deepening of processing of raw materials;
- to increase the competitiveness of local goods in the foreign market based on the expansion and diversification of the range of manufactured products, the development of new types of products and the development of high technologies;
- paying special attention to the introduction of resource-saving and high-performance technologies in network enterprises;
- State promotion of attracting domestic and foreign investments in production of high-tech products and technical-technological modernization of the industry;
- acceleration of scientific placement, zoning and specialization of branch enterprises close to raw material sources and saving transport costs;
- strengthening of integrated relations between raw material producers and raw material processing industrial enterprises by means of cluster, cooperation and other structures;
- acceleration of decommissioning of outdated technical means and equipment and equipping production with modern equipment and technologies;
- textile and leather-shoe industry due to the production of competitive finished products and semi-finished products, including dyed yarn, fabric, treated leather, knitwear, sewing, footwear and leather-leather goods, which are in demand in the domestic and world markets, based on deep processing of local raw materials further improve the structure.

Studying the experience of advanced foreign countries with highly developed clusters shows that in the conditions of "globalization" and "knowledge economy", clusters are becoming one of the main sources of innovative development. Therefore, the participation of "knowledge and innovation block", that is, universities, scientific research institutions, testing laboratories, venture funds and start-up projects, is considered one of the main

conditions within the clusters of developed countries. In Japan's clustering policy, one or more universities (scientific research institutions) are attached and responsible for each cluster group based on its specialization.

In our opinion, every cluster being formed in our republic should form centers (laboratories) of "Innovative developments and introduction of new business ideas" and attach leading universities and research institutes to them based on the specialization of the cluster, scientific and innovative centers, venture funds and it is desirable to establish strong cooperation with companies.

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